

Entanglement-Based Crossbar for Quantum Routers

Jessica Illiano *Member, IEEE*, Caterina De Risi,
Marcello Caleffi *Senior Member, IEEE*, Angela Sara Cacciapuoti *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Classical crossbar routers cannot be directly adopted in the quantum domain, due to the laws of quantum mechanics. In this paper, we propose an *entanglement-based crossbar* as the quantum counterpart of the classical switching fabric, enabling generalized forwarding solely through local Pauli measurements on a multipartite entangled resource, acting as a switching fabric. We formalize the notions of blocking and non-blocking conditions in the quantum domain by providing the design tenets to achieve non-blocking switching fabric. Then, we introduce the edge-controlled design principle, by identifying the minimal 2×2 non-blocking base unit as the fundamental building block for scalable router architectures. The proposed framework provides a hardware-agnostic and scalable foundation for quantum routers, bridging classical network theory with quantum-native forwarding.

Index Terms—Multipartite Entanglement, quantum router, switching fabric, quantum forwarding, ERC-CoG QNattyNet.

I. INTRODUCTION

In classical networks, the core of a router is the switching fabric, namely, the component responsible for transferring packets from an input port to an output port according to the routing decisions. The advent of crossbar-based architectures replaced early shared-medium interconnects with high-throughput fabrics, capable of connecting any input port to any output port in a collision-free and deterministic manner. By physically establishing input-output paths, these fabrics enabled efficient packet forwarding and became the cornerstone of scalable router design in classical networks.

However, this concept cannot be directly transposed to the quantum domain, where the physical transmission and duplication of quantum information are fundamentally constrained by the no-cloning theorem and the quantum measurement postulate. Instead, quantum communication is built upon a fundamentally different resource, quantum entanglement, which replaces the concept of information flow with that of entanglement distribution [1]. Consequently, the notion of “forwarding” must also be redefined [1], [2]: it no longer denotes the relay of bit-packets through intermediate nodes, but rather the end-to-end distribution of entangled qubits via entanglement manipulation [1], [2]. This paradigm, recently termed *entanglement forwarding* [1], extends the classical store-and-forward into a quantum-native domain.

The authors are with the www.QuantumInternet.it research group, University of Naples Federico II, Naples, 80125 Italy.

This work has been funded by the European Union under the ERC grant QNattyNet, n.101169850. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Building on these considerations, in this paper we propose an *entanglement-based* crossbar for quantum routers¹, serving as the quantum counterpart of the classical switching fabric. Specifically, we investigate how multipartite entangled states can be engineered to function as quantum crossbars that enable entanglement forwarding between input and output ports, through local Pauli measurements and local unitaries.

The proposed entanglement-based approach fundamentally differs from hardware-driven photonic or optomechanical routers, as it replaces wiring with entanglement links, activated adaptively, thereby providing a hardware-agnostic solution. Moreover, as discussed in the Related Work section, this proposal also markedly differs from the existing state-of-the-art, representing the first step towards a fully quantum-native design for router architectures.

A. Related Work & Contributions

In the context of quantum networks, extensive research has been devoted to designing devices that enable node interconnection and entanglement distribution. However, given the early stage conceptualization of quantum networks, consistent nomenclature and clear functional definitions for the quantum counterparts of classical network devices, such as repeaters, switches, and routers, are still lacking. Quantum repeaters were originally conceived to extend the range of entanglement distribution through entanglement swapping, with successive generations incorporating entanglement purification and quantum error correction [3]. In the literature, the concepts of quantum switch and quantum router generalize this functionality to multi-user or multi-hop settings, enabling end-to-end entanglement distribution among distant nodes [?], [4]–[11]. Across these works, a common bipartite-based design paradigm can be identified: routers, switches, and repeaters are modeled as intermediate devices supporting end-to-end entanglement distribution by generating or manipulating EPR pairs through Bell-state measurements (BSMs). Their operational mode is constrained by resource availability, such as the number of point-to-point entangled links, quantum memory capacity, fidelity, and entanglement generation rate. Consequently, most investigations analyze these devices as components of a larger networked systems, with the device itself abstracted as a functional entity executing BSM operations or scheduling EPR generation according to a routing metric or optimization algorithms. Conversely, contributions that directly examine device-level functionality, focus primarily on hardware-oriented design [12]–[14]. To the best of

¹In this work, we adopt the term *quantum router* to emphasize network-level entanglement forwarding beyond local-area interconnections.

our knowledge, only limited efforts have explored the use of multipartite entanglement as a foundational resource for network-level devices. In [15], a multipartite entangled state was used to embed entanglement purification within a repeater protocol. However, a systematic investigation of multipartite entanglement as an architectural resource for quantum routers remains an open and unexplored direction. Motivated by this gap, we propose an architectural framework that leverages multipartite entanglement for quantum router design.

Our contributions are as follows:

- We formalize the notion of *entanglement-based crossbar* as the quantum analog of a classical switching fabric, realizing forwarding through Pauli measurements.
- We map classical switching properties, namely blocking and non-blocking, into operational conditions for entanglement-based crossbars, and derive the design principles required to achieve a *non-blocking* quantum fabric.
- We introduce the *edge-controlled design principle* and identify the minimal 2×2 non-blocking base unit as the fundamental building block for scalable router architectures.

The proposed framework represents a first step towards a hardware-agnostic and scalable foundation for quantum routers.

II. BACKGROUND

Here we outline the preliminaries that are used throughout the remainder of the paper.

Graph states constitute a versatile class of multipartite entangled states for quantum networking [16], [17]. An n -qubit graph state has the useful property of admitting a one-to-one correspondence with a graph representation, providing an intuitive mapping between the qubit interaction pattern and the adjacency structure of the associated graph [18]. Accordingly, a graph state $|G\rangle$ is univocally associated with a graph $G = (V, E)$, where each vertex $a \in V$, with $|V| = n$, represents a qubit, and each edge $a, b \in E$ denotes a controlled- Z operation between qubits a and b . Indeed, owing to this one-to-one mapping, single-qubit Pauli measurements, $\{\sigma_\chi\}$ with $\chi \in \{x, y, z\}$, performed on the qubits of a graph state can be translated into the corresponding graph-level operations. Indeed, the post-measurement graph is obtained – up to local unitaries – by applying the graph transformations as described in [18], [19], namely vertex deletion for σ_z , local complementation for σ_y , and nested local complementations for σ_x measurements. The mathematical formulations and derivations can be found in [16]–[18].

Definition 1 (Measurement strategy). *Let A be a finite index set of qubits in V . A measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ is a function that assigns to each qubit $i \in A$ a label $\chi_i \in \{x, y, z\}$, indicating which single-qubit Pauli measurement, $\sigma_{\chi_i}^i$, must be performed on i :*

$$\gamma(i) = \sigma_{\chi_i}^i, \quad \forall i \in A, \text{ with } \chi_i \in \{x, y, z\}. \quad (1)$$

Accordingly, given a strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$, the corresponding overall Pauli operator acting on A is: $\mathcal{P}_\gamma^A \triangleq \bigotimes_{i \in A} \sigma_{\chi_i}^i$. If the global system is a larger set of qubits, $V \supseteq A$, we use the natural embedding so that \mathcal{P}_γ^V acts as identity on qubits outside² A :

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V \triangleq \left(\bigotimes_{i \in A} \sigma_{\chi_i}^i \right) \otimes \left(\bigotimes_{j \in V \setminus A} I^{(j)} \right). \quad (2)$$

Definition 2 (Achievability). *Let $|G\rangle$ be a graph state associated with the graph $G = (V, E)$, and let $G' = (V', E')$ denote the targeted graph specified by a desired connection pattern. We say that G' is achievable through a measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ if there exists a subset of qubits $A \subseteq V$ such that:*

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V |G\rangle \stackrel{LU}{=} |G'\rangle \otimes |\phi_{idle}\rangle, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{P}_γ^V is the global Pauli operator defined in (2), $|G'\rangle$ is the post-measurement state corresponding to the graph G' , and $|\phi_{idle}\rangle$ denotes the residual state on the subsystem of qubits $V \setminus (V' \cup A)$.

Accordingly to Def. 2, a targeted state $|G'\rangle$ is decoupled from the residual state defined on the subsystem of qubits $V \setminus (V' \cup A)$, via the measurement strategy. The vertices in A on which the measurement strategy γ acts through Pauli measurements are consequently removed from the original graph. Hence, each achievable graph G' can be associated with a specific *depleted set* of vertices, namely those measured to transform the initial graph into the desired targeted graph G' . This concept is formalized as follows.

Definition 3 (Depleted set). *Given a graph state $|G\rangle$ associated with a graph $G = (V, E)$ and a measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$, the depleted set $\Gamma(G') \subseteq V$ corresponding to an achievable graph G' is defined as $\Gamma(G') \triangleq \{i \in V \mid \gamma(i) = \sigma_{\chi_i}^i, \text{ with } \chi_i \in \{x, y, z\}\}$. The set $\Gamma(G')$ thus contains the vertices measured under $\gamma(\cdot)$ to obtain the connection pattern described by G' .*

III. ENTANGLEMENT-BASED CROSSBAR DESIGN

As discussed in Sec. I, the objective of a quantum router is to dynamically interconnect any set of disjoint pairs of *input-port qubit* and *output-port qubit*, thereby realizing the forwarding functionality in the quantum domain. We note that we adopted the classical router terminology for the sake of clarity. To this aim, a graph state $|G\rangle$ is used as the fundamental resource underpinning the operation of the switching fabric. Accordingly, we define $I = \{i_1, \dots, i_N\}$ and $O = \{o_1, \dots, o_N\}$ as the sets of input- and output-port qubits, respectively, which are disjoint subsets of the vertex set, i.e., $I \cup O = V$ and $I \cap O = \emptyset$.

With this in mind, the achievable graph G' introduced in Def. 2 corresponds to the graph obtained by properly manipulating the original graph G , to activate a set of the

²In (2), we used the common notation abuse of omitting the explicit tensor order. This simplification improves readability, although the ordering in the tensor product remains meaningful.

mentioned disjoint interconnections between input- and output-port qubits, as formally captured by the following definition.

Definition 4 (Matching Set). *Let $|G\rangle$ be a graph state associated with a graph $G = (V, E)$, where $V = I \cup O$ is partitioned into two disjoint subsets of port qubits: the input-ports $I = i_1, \dots, i_N$ and the output-ports $O = o_1, \dots, o_N$. The matching set $E' \subset I \times O$, with $|E'| \leq N$ represents the desired pattern of entanglement links established between disjoint input- and output-port pairs, as a result of a measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ applied to the resource state $|G\rangle$, i.e.:*

$$|G'\rangle \stackrel{\text{LU}}{=} \bigotimes_{(i,o) \in E'} |\Phi_{io}\rangle, \quad (4)$$

where $\stackrel{\text{LU}}{=}$ denotes the equivalence up to local unitaries and $|\Phi_{io}\rangle$ is a Bell state shared between i and o . The corresponding achieved graph $G' = (V', E')$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} G' &= (V', E'), \text{ with} \\ V' &= \{i, o \mid (i, o) \in E'\} \subseteq I \cup O, \\ E' &= \{(i_i, o_j), (i_k, o_r) \mid i_i, i_k \in I \wedge o_j, o_r \in O, \\ &\text{with } i_i \neq i_k, o_j \neq o_r\}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Accordingly to Def. 4, the edges in E' specify the dynamic connection pattern, or *forwarding configuration*, realized by the quantum router in a single operational round. The vertices in V' correspond to the *active ports* participating in the current matching, while all remaining port qubits in $(I \cup O) \setminus V'$ are referred to as *idle ports*. In the following, for notational simplicity and with a slight notation abuse, we will use the symbols G' , V' , and E' interchangeably when referring to the achieved configuration. In particular, we introduce the unified symbol \mathcal{M} to denote either G' , V' , or E' , with the intended meaning clear from the context.

Definition 5 (N -Crossbar resource). *Let $|G\rangle$ be the graph state associated with the graph $G = (V, E)$, whose vertex set is partitioned into the input- and output-ports, i.e., $V = I \cup O$. Then $|G\rangle$ is a valid N -crossbar resource if for any matching $\mathcal{M} \subset I \times O$ as defined in Def. 4, with $|I| = |O| = N$ and $|\mathcal{M}| \leq N$ there exists a measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ acting on the qubits in V such that:*

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V |G\rangle \stackrel{\text{LU}}{=} |G'\rangle \otimes |\phi_{idle}\rangle, \quad (6)$$

where $|G'\rangle$ denotes the disjoint entangled pairs achieved through $\gamma(\cdot)$ as in (4), and $|\phi_{idle}\rangle$ has been defined in Def. 2.

As represented in the leftmost part of Fig. 1, the simplest example of a crossbar resource is a 3-qubit GHZ state, where i_1 acts as an input qubit and o_1, o_2 as output qubits. The input-output connection between the pair i_1, o_j is realized through a Pauli measurement on the remaining output-port qubit $o_r, r \neq j$. In principle, this elementary resource could be scaled, as represented in the rightmost part of Fig. 1, where the sets of input- and output-port qubits are interconnected through a graph state associated with a complete bipartite

Fig. 1: Graph representation of a GHZ-equivalent graph state as an entanglement crossbar. Only one stable connection can be achieved through Pauli measurement at the port qubits.

Fig. 2: Binary star state as a crossbar with two switching qubits (grey circles). Only one stable connection can be achieved by measuring both port qubits and switching qubits.

graph. However, it's easy to verify that any measurement strategy only achieves matchings with $|\mathcal{M}| = 1$. Hence, this design remains trivial and functionally naive as well, since GHZ-equivalent states correspond to a crossbar enabling only one connection.

To design scalable entanglement-based crossbars, it is therefore necessary to reinterpret the notion of blocking and non-blocking operative modes from classical switching theory and map them into the quantum domain, where forwarding is realized through local operations and measurements rather than wired electronic components. Classically, a switching device with N inputs and N outputs is said to be *non-blocking* if it is always possible to connect any idle input to any idle output³, where the term *idle* refers to an input- or output-port that is not currently engaged in any active connection within the switching fabric. With this in mind, we formulate Lemma 1.

Lemma 1 (Blocking Condition). *Let I and O be the sets of input- and output-port qubits of an N -crossbar resource $|G\rangle$, with $|I| = |O| = N$. The crossbar resource $|G\rangle$ is blocking if there exists a targeted graph $G' = (V', E')$ with $E' \subset I \times O$ and $|E'| < N$ such that, for every measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ that achieves G' , it holds that $\Gamma(G') \cap ((I \cup O) \setminus V') \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof: Let $G' = (V', E')$, with $|V'|$ active input-output ports, be the achievable graph. Since $|E'| < N$, at least one input and one output port remain *idle* under the target configuration G' , i.e., $V \setminus V' \neq \emptyset$. By hypothesis, for every measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ that achieves G' , there exists at least one port $i_p \in \Gamma(G') \cap (V \setminus V')$ (or equivalently o_p , since the argument applies symmetrically for $i_p \in I$ or $o_p \in O$). Hence, although i_p is an idle port, it is nonetheless measured, and thus depleted, in the process of realizing G' , being

³Different formulations of the non-blocking property exist. We adopted the definition introduced in the early work on switching networks [20].

removed from the original graph. This, in turn, implies that i_p can no longer be used to establish additional entanglement-based connections by local operations and classical communication (LOCC). Let o_q denote an idle port on the opposite side of the crossbar (if $i_p \in I$, then $o_q \in O \setminus V'$ and vice-versa). The pair (i_p, o_q) constitutes an *idle* input-output port pair that cannot be subsequently connected, since i_p is no longer available. This directly violates the non-blocking criterion, which requires that any idle input can be connected to any idle output without disturbing existing connections. Hence, the crossbar resource $|G\rangle$ is *blocking*. ■

Remark (Switching qubits). *The definition of blocking introduced in this work extends the classical notion of connection stability to the quantum domain. Indeed, a non-blocking quantum router design must preserve the ability to establish a stable number of connections, i.e., N , between input- and output-ports, regardless of prior configurations. Lemma 1 shows that this property cannot be achieved by a multipartite entangled state involving only port qubits. Hence, an additional layer of connectivity is required in the router design. Specifically, by increasing entanglement structural complexity, we introduce a distinct class of qubits, termed switching qubits, that mediate entanglement forwarding between input and output ports, enabling a non-blocking operational mode.*

Stemming from the above, achieving the non-blocking condition in an entanglement-based crossbar requires that all ports, including those not currently engaged in a specific matching, remain capable of being interconnected through entanglement. Thus, a non-blocking crossbar must support the extraction of Bell states between *any combination of input and output ports*, ensuring full reconfigurability of the forwarding pattern. Consequently, the parameter N introduced in Def. 5 denotes not only the number of input- and output-ports but also the maximum number of Bell states that are simultaneously extracted from the crossbar resource $|G\rangle$. This capability directly depends on the chosen resource $|G\rangle$.

By introducing the switching qubits, the graph associated with the considered graph state has to be redefined as $G = (V, E)$, where the augmented vertex set $V = I \cup O \cup S$ collects the disjoint sets I and O of input- and output-port qubits, and the set S of *switching qubits*. The edge set E captures the entanglement connections among these vertices. However, the mere presence of switching qubits is not sufficient to guarantee the non-blocking condition. For instance, the binary star state [16], illustrated in Fig. 2, includes two *switching qubits* but still constitutes a *blocking* crossbar resource. We formalize the conditions required for a non-blocking resource in the following design principle.

Design Principle 1 (Non-Blocking Entanglement-Based Crossbars). *Consider a graph state $|G\rangle$ serving as an N -crossbar resource with vertex partition $V = I \cup O \cup S$, where I and O are the disjoint input- and output-port sets ($I \cap O = \emptyset$), and S is the switching-qubit set disjoint from the ports ($S \cap (I \cup O) = \emptyset$). The resource $|G\rangle$ is said to realize a*

Fig. 3: Representation of the *edge-controlled* crossbar with $N = 2$ (left) and $N = 4$ (right)

non-blocking N -crossbar if the following conditions hold:

- I) *For any matching $\mathcal{M} \subset I \times O$ with $|\mathcal{M}| < N$ and any measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$ achieving \mathcal{M} by operating exclusively on the switching qubits S , the global operator \mathcal{P}_γ^V applied to $|G\rangle$ yields a tensor product between the targeted graph $|G'\rangle$, encoding \mathcal{M} , and a residual graph state $|G''\rangle$ on the idle subsystem $V \setminus (V' \cup \Gamma(G'))$ of the form:*

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V |G\rangle \stackrel{\text{LU}}{=} |G'\rangle \otimes |G''\rangle; \quad (7)$$

- II) *The residual graph $|G''\rangle$ is itself a **non-blocking** $(N - |\mathcal{M}|)$ -crossbar, i.e., $|G''\rangle$ satisfies the design principle I recursively.*

Condition I guarantees that any matching \mathcal{M} that does not saturate the entanglement-based crossbar capacity ($|\mathcal{M}| < N$) can be realized without depleting the port qubits and without exhausting the underlying entangled resource. Thus, the remaining unmeasured subsystem retains a valid crossbar structure, which in turn allows the establishment of new connections among the idle ports. Condition II extends this property recursively, by ensuring that the residual resource maintains the same capability, so that any pair of idle ports can always be interconnected through entanglement. Together, these conditions realize the non-blocking behavior of the crossbar in the quantum domain.

Building on this tenet of non-blocking entanglement-based crossbar, we introduce the *Edge-Controlled (EC)* crossbar, namely an entanglement-based crossbar that guarantees the non-blocking behavior. According to this design, a dedicated switching qubit is associated with every input-output interconnection. More precisely, an edge-controlled resource $|G_{\text{EC}}\rangle$ is defined as the graph state obtained by enriching the complete bipartite graph $|K_N\rangle$ as formally described below.

EC Resource. *Let $K_N = (V_K, E_K)$ be the complete bipartite graph with vertex partition $V_K = I \cup O$, where $I = \{i_1, \dots, i_N\}$ and $O = \{o_1, \dots, o_N\}$ are the disjoint sets of input- and output-port qubits, respectively, and $E_K = \{(i, o), \forall i \in I, o \in O\} = I \times O$. The Edge-Controlled (EC) resource state $|G_{\text{EC}}\rangle$ is the graph state associated with the graph $G_{\text{EC}} = (V, E)$ obtained by enriching K_N through the introduction of a dedicated switching qubit $s_{i,o}$ for each edge*

$(i, o) \in E_K$. Each new vertex $s_{i,o}$ has exactly two adjacent vertices, namely the endpoints i and o , thereby replacing each direct edge (i, o) of K_N with a two-hop path traversing $s_{i,o}$:

$$V \triangleq I \cup O \cup S, \quad (8)$$

$$S \triangleq \{s_{i,o} \mid (i, o) \in E_K \text{ with } \text{Adj}(s_{i,o}) = \{i, o\}\}, \quad (9)$$

$$E \triangleq \{(i, s_{i,o}), (s_{i,o}, o) \mid (i, o) \in E_K\}. \quad (10)$$

The resulting structure, illustrated in Fig. 3, defines the *Edge-Controlled (EC) resource state*. It is clear that each switching qubit controls the activation or inhibition of a direct entanglement link between the corresponding input qubit i and output qubit o , through local Pauli measurements.

The EC structure induces a natural partition of the switching-qubit set S once a matching is realized. Specifically, given a matching $E' \subset I \times O$ as in Def. 4, it is possible to identify the sets of active input- and output-ports as $I' \triangleq \{i \in I \mid \exists! o \in O : (i, o) \in E'\}$ and $O' \triangleq \{o \in O \mid \exists! i \in I : (i, o) \in E'\}$. Stemming from these sets, the switching set S can be partitioned as follows:

- **Mediators:** the switching qubits involved in activating the matching E' :

$$S_{\text{med}}(E') \triangleq \{s_{i,o} \in S \mid (i, o) \in E'\}. \quad (11)$$

- **Competitors:** the switching qubits associated with edges connecting an active port either to idle ports or to other active ports not belonging to the current matching E' :

$$S_C(E') \triangleq \{s_{i,o} \in S \mid (i, o) \in [(I' \times O) \cup (I \times O')] \setminus E'\}. \quad (12)$$

- **Unused:** the switching qubits associated with edges connecting idle ports, i.e.:

$$S_{\text{idle}}(E') \triangleq \{s_{i,o} \in S \mid i \notin I' \wedge o \notin O'\}. \quad (13)$$

Accordingly, the mediators determine the direct connections as specified by E' , the competitors represent potentially conflicting links incident to active ports, and the unused switching qubits correspond to the idle portion of the crossbar.

In the following proposition, we prove that the EC resource is non-blocking.

Proposition 1 (Non-Blocking Edge-Controlled N -Crossbar). *Let $|G_{\text{EC}}\rangle$ be a N -EC crossbar resource. For any matching $\mathcal{M} \subset I \times O$, the EC resource is non-blocking accordingly to Design Principle 1.*

Proof: Accordingly to Design Principle 1, an entanglement-based crossbar is non-blocking if for any matching, there exists a measurement strategy resulting in (7) and the residual state is still a non-blocking crossbar resource. The proof proceeds in steps:

Consider the matching associated with $E' \subset I \times O$ as introduced above, together with the three EC-induced subsets of switching qubits $S_{\text{idle}}(E')$, $S_C(E')$, and $S_{\text{med}}(E')$.

Step 1 (Per-edge strategy and port safety). Let us consider the following measurement strategy:

$$\gamma(s_{i,o}) = \begin{cases} \sigma_y & s_{i,o} \in S_{\text{med}}(E') \\ \sigma_z & s_{i,o} \in S_C(E') \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

According to this strategy, for each $(i, o) \in E'$, a Pauli- Y is performed on the corresponding mediator $s_{i,o} \in S_{\text{med}}(E')$, while Pauli- Z measurements are applied to the competitors $S_C(E')$, and nothing is done on the other switching qubits. A Pauli- Y measurement on $s_{i,o}$ enables (up to local unitaries on the neighbors) a direct edge between its adjacent vertexes i and o , i.e., (i, o) , and removes $s_{i,o}$ from the graph [16], [18], [19], [21]. Similarly, the Pauli- Z measurements delete all the competitor switching qubits and all their incident edges, without altering the rest of the graph. We note that each switching qubit $s_{i,o}$ is uniquely associated with its pair (i, o) , thus the measurements specified by $\gamma(\cdot)$ act on pairwise disjoint sets of switching qubits, i.e., on $S_{\text{med}}(E') \cup S_C(E')$, with $S_{\text{med}}(E') \cap S_C(E') = \emptyset$. This in turn implies that port qubits are never measured, that is, *ports are never depleted*:

$$\Gamma(G') = S_{\text{med}}(E') \cup S_C(E') \subseteq S \wedge \Gamma(G') \cap (I \cup O) = \emptyset. \quad (15)$$

Step 2 (Commutation and independence). The EC structure ensures that all switching qubits in $S_{\text{med}}(E') \cup S_C(E')$ are distinct. Thus, the corresponding single-qubit Pauli operators commute, since they act on disjoint subsets of qubits [22]. As a consequence, the measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$, performed on $S_{\text{med}}(E') \cup S_C(E')$, yields the same post-measurement state, regardless of order:

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V |G_{\text{EC}}\rangle \stackrel{\text{LU}}{=} |G'\rangle \otimes |\phi_{\text{idle}}\rangle, \quad (16)$$

where $|G'\rangle = \bigotimes_{(i,o) \in E'} |\Phi_{io}\rangle$ is the achieved graph with edge set E' , and $|\phi_{\text{idle}}\rangle$ is the post-measurement state on the remaining subsystem $V \setminus (V' \cup \Gamma(G'))$ with $\Gamma(G') = S_{\text{med}}(E') \cup S_C(E')$.

Step 3 (Structure of the residual and recursion). As proved above, the depleted set is $\Gamma(G')$ as expressed in (15). Therefore, the residual subsystem is:

$$V_{\text{idle}} = V \setminus (V' \cup \Gamma(G')) = \quad (17)$$

$$\left((I \setminus I') \cup (O \setminus O') \right) \cup \left(S \setminus (S_C(E') \cup S_{\text{med}}(E')) \right).$$

For any two *idle* ports $i \in I \setminus I'$ and $o \in O \setminus O'$, the switching qubit $s_{i,o} \in S_{\text{idle}}(E')$ remains present and adjacent only to *both* endpoints, as it is unaffected by the measurement strategy $\gamma(\cdot)$. Hence, the EC structure is preserved among the idle ports. More into details, the residual subsystem $|\phi_{\text{idle}}\rangle$ is, up to local unitaries, equivalent to the graph state $|G''_{\text{EC}}\rangle$, with vertex set $(I \setminus I') \cup (O \setminus O') \cup (S \setminus \Gamma(G'))$ and edge set $\{(i, s_{i,o}), (s_{i,o}, o) \mid i \notin I' \wedge o \notin O'\}$, which reproduces the $(N - |E'|)$ -EC crossbar structure in (8)-(10). Overall, (16) can be re-written as:

$$\mathcal{P}_\gamma^V |G_{\text{EC}}\rangle \stackrel{\text{LU}}{=} \bigotimes_{(i,o) \in E'} |\Phi_{io}\rangle \otimes |G''_{\text{EC}}\rangle. \quad (18)$$

Step 4 (Non-blocking property). By repeating Steps 1–3 on $|G''_{EC}\rangle$ for any further matching among the idle ports, we see that the same construction applies inductively. Therefore the residual $|G''_{EC}\rangle$ is itself a non-blocking $(N - |E'|)$ -crossbar in the sense of Design Principle 1.

This completes the proof by establishing that $|G_{EC}\rangle$ is a non-blocking N -crossbar. ■

In essence, the non-blocking property of the EC crossbar arises from two *invariants* of the proposed design: *the port-safety* and *the disjoint-switching-domain* properties. Each switching qubit mediates an independent input–output connection, ensuring that partial measurements never deplete the port qubits nor disturb unconnected edges. Consequently, the residual subsystem consistently preserves the same EC structure, thereby maintaining the non-blocking operational mode recursively. Therefore, new direct entanglement links can always be established on top of an existing entanglement forwarding configuration by performing Pauli measurements only on idle switching qubits, while port qubits remain untouched.

Remark (Base Unit). *Accordingly, the edge-controlled design provides intrinsic flexibility in achieving arbitrary matchings. Such flexibility is evident in the simplest configuration such as the 2-EC crossbar shown in Fig. 3, where, by acting locally on distinct switching qubits, one can realize either the parallel matching $\{(i_1, o_1), (i_2, o_2)\}$ or the cross matching $\{(i_1, o_2), (i_2, o_1)\}$ without generating a new resource. This property cannot be achieved with GHZ-equivalent or bipartite-only constructions, where the absence of mediator qubits forces destructive measurement patterns.*

We envision that the 2-EC module supports crossbar scalability: by interconnecting multiple 2-EC modules as *base units*, larger crossbars can be assembled in Clos-like architectures while preserving the non-blocking behavior. Indeed, since each switching qubit controls a single edge independently, the resulting composite architectures can maintain local configurability and a form of connection isolation. Hence, the 2-EC resource represents a promising baseline acting as a fundamental building block for scalable, and strictly non-blocking entanglement-based crossbars.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This work introduced entanglement-based crossbars as the quantum counterpart of classical switching fabrics. Building on the concept of generalized forwarding, we formalized blocking and non-blocking conditions in the quantum domain. We exploited the features of multipartite entanglement and demonstrated that switching qubits are necessary to achieve a non-blocking operational mode. Finally, we proposed the *edge-controlled* design principle for obtaining a non-blocking entanglement-based crossbar, identified the 2-EC configuration as a base unit for scalable quantum routers. These results provide a foundation for hardware-agnostic, scalable quantum routers and open the way towards generalized entanglement

forwarding via multipartite entanglement in the Quantum Internet.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Caleffi and A. S. Cacciapuoti, “Quantum internet architecture: unlocking quantum-native routing via quantum addressing,” *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, pp. 1–1, 2026.
- [2] A. Abane, M. Cubeddu, V. S. Mai, and A. Battou, “Entanglement routing in quantum networks: A comprehensive survey,” *IEEE TQE*, 2025.
- [3] S. Muralidharan, L. Li, J. Kim, N. Lütkenhaus, M. D. Lukin, and L. Jiang, “Optimal architectures for long distance quantum communication,” *Scientific reports*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–10, 2016.
- [4] N. Benchasattabuse, M. Hajdušek, and R. Van Meter, “Architecture and protocols for all-photonic quantum repeaters,” in *2024 IEEE QCE*, vol. 1, pp. 1879–1889, IEEE, 2024.
- [5] N. Benchasattabuse, M. Hajdušek, and R. Van Meter, “Engineering challenges in all-photonic quantum repeaters,” *IEEE Network*, vol. 39, no. 1, pp. 132–139, 2024.
- [6] J. Illiano, A. S. Cacciapuoti, A. Manzalini, and M. Caleffi, “The impact of the quantum data plane overhead on the throughput,” in *Proc. of ACM NANOCOM '21*, pp. 1–6, 2021.
- [7] Á. G. Iñesta, H. Choi, D. Englund, and S. Wehner, “Quantum circuit switching with one-way repeaters in star networks,” in *2024 IEEE QCE*, vol. 1, pp. 1857–1867, IEEE, 2024.
- [8] K. Lemr and A. Černoch, “Linear-optical programmable quantum router,” *Optics Communications*, vol. 300, pp. 282–285, 2013.
- [9] W. Shi and R. Malaney, “Quantum routing for emerging quantum networks,” *IEEE Network*, 2023.
- [10] P. Promponas, V. Valls, and L. Tassiulas, “Quantum switch scheduling for information qubits,” *SIGMETRICS Perform. Eval. Rev.*, vol. 51, p. 78–80, oct 2023.
- [11] S. Gauthier, G. Vardoyan, and S. Wehner, “An architecture for control of entanglement generation switches in quantum networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Quantum Engineering*, vol. 4, pp. 1–17, 2023.
- [12] M. Azari, P. Polakos, and K. P. Seshadreesan, “Quantum switches for gottesman-kitaev-preskill qubit-based all-photonic quantum networks,” *IEEE Transactions on Quantum Engineering*, 2024.
- [13] J. Kuang, “A optical quantum router based on ghz states,” in *2019 IEEE ITNEC*, pp. 2540–2544, IEEE, 2019.
- [14] J. Cumbrado and R. Puebla, “Quantum switches for single-photon routing and entanglement generation in waveguide-based networks,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:2503.10276*, 2025.
- [15] K. Azuma, K. Tamaki, and H.-K. Lo, “All-photonic quantum repeaters,” *Nature communications*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2015.
- [16] S.-Y. Chen, J. Illiano, A. S. Cacciapuoti, and M. Caleffi, “Entanglement-based artificial topology: Neighboring remote network nodes,” *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, 2025.
- [17] F. Mazza, M. Caleffi, and A. S. Cacciapuoti, “Quantum lan: On-demand network topology via two-colorable graph states,” in *QCNC 2024*, pp. 127–134, IEEE, 2024.
- [18] M. Hein, W. Dür, J. Eisert, R. Raussendorf, M. Nest, and H.-J. Briegel, “Entanglement in graph states and its applications,” *arXiv preprint quant-ph/0602096*, 2006.
- [19] M. Hein, J. Eisert, and H. J. Briegel, “Multiparty entanglement in graph states,” *Physical Review A*, vol. 69, no. 6, p. 062311, 2004.
- [20] C. Clos, “A study of non-blocking switching networks,” *Bell System Technical Journal*, vol. 32, no. 2, pp. 406–424, 1953.
- [21] F. Mazza, M. Caleffi, and A. S. Cacciapuoti, “Intra-qlan connectivity via graph states: Beyond the physical topology,” *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*, vol. 12, no. 2, pp. 870–887, 2025.
- [22] M. A. Nielsen and I. L. Chuang, *Quantum Computation and Quantum Information*. Cambridge University Press, 2011.